

ORTHOTROPIC RHEOLOGY OF GLASS-MAT-REINFORCED THERMOPLASTICS (GMT): LUBRICATED SQUEEZING FLOW

M. A. Dweib and C. M. Ó Brádaigh
Composites Research Unit,
Department of Mechanical Engineering,
National University of Ireland, Galway.
Tel: + 353 91 750424, Fax: + 353 91 750534

SUMMARY: The rheological behaviour of Glass-Mat Reinforced Thermoplastics (GMT) was studied under isothermal compression moulding conditions on a universal test machine. The anisotropic behaviour of the lubricated squeezing flow is modelled using three non-Newtonian extensional viscosities. Previous work modelled the material as transversely isotropic, resulting in two in-plane extensional viscosities. In that work, the main assumption was that the material had the same viscosity in one of the in-plane directions and through thickness. Consideration of three independent viscosities is considered necessary as a result of an extensive research study of the fibre structure and orientation of the material, which shows that the material has different fibre structures in three different directions.

KEYWORDS: Rheology, GMT, Squeeze flow, Anisotropy

INTRODUCTION

The squeezing flow of polymer composites (thermoplastic matrix reinforced by continuous glass fibre) was investigated in this work because of the importance of this material in manufacturing industrial parts for automotive and non-automotive applications [1]. The governing viscosities of the flowing material, the filling time, how far the filling is achieved when different and complicated shapes are considered, and the homogeneity and mechanical properties (strength) of the final products are thus urgently important.

GMT-PP 30% glass fibre material manufactured by PCD-Polymer, Austria was investigated in this research study and displayed anisotropic results under lubricated compression moulding as shown in Figure 1. In the previous work [2, 3], the squeeze flow process was modelled accordingly to accommodate this behaviour and a transversely isotropic model was introduced to give a mathematical representation to the squeezing process. The transversely isotropic model was used to characterise two different viscosities in the two in-plane directions because the flow pattern followed an elliptical rather than a circular shape, Figure 1. The model considered that the material is governed by two main viscosities in two orthogonal directions and was solved for the Newtonian case [2] and for the non-Newtonian case [3]. The major assumption in using the transversely isotropic model is that the viscosity through thickness was assumed to be equal to the viscosity in one of the in-plane directions. The two in-plane viscosities were determined depending on the geometrical shape which was elliptical. That enabled the derivation of a relationship between two strain rates and then two viscosities were calculated.

Figure 1: Photograph showing an original circular specimen (left) and a squeezed specimen (right) [4]

MATERIAL

GMT-PP, 30% glass fibre manufactured by PCD-Polymere, Austria, was used in this research study. The matrix material is polypropylene, and it contains swirled continuous glass fibre (Figure 2), showing the fibre structure of the material after burning off the matrix in a convection oven at 500 °C for 4 to 5 hours. The material (commercially known as Daplen TC-GMT) is available as semi-finished sheets containing 30% glass fibre by weight [5]. The sheets are manufactured by impregnating glass mats with thermoplastic matrix on double belt presses by extruding a thermoplastic melt between two or more chemically or mechanically bonded glass mats.

Figure 2: Photograph of the fibre after burning off the matrix

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The fully lubricated, circular mould was set up on a universal 100 kN hydraulic Instron test machine and heated to 180°C. 50 mm diameter circular disks (3.7 mm thick) of 30% continuous glass fibre mat were isothermally squeezed to 20% of their original thickness. Figure 3 shows a sample of experimental load versus displacement results at different closing speeds (squeezing rates).

Figure 3: Plate displacement Vs load, one GMT layer, 180 °C, 50 mm diameter disks. At different squeezing rates.

The elliptical shapes (Figure 1) which resulted from squeezing circular disks of GMT can be modelled as shown in Figure 4. Using the previous relationship [2, 3] between the major and minor axes of the elliptically deformed specimens:

$$\frac{r_1}{r_2} = e \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\Delta r_1}{\Delta r_2} = f \quad (2)$$

Figures 4 and 5 show how e and f vary with mould separation distance (h). f was taken as a constant (Figure 4) at any mould plate separation (h) while e is a variable with h (Figure 5).

Taking into consideration that the material deforms at constant volume, three different strain rates can be derived in the three directions x , y and z where x and y are identical to the major and minor axes of the elliptically deformed specimen while z denotes the through thickness direction:

$$\dot{\epsilon}_{xx} = \frac{fu}{(e+f)h} \quad (3)$$

Figure 4: $\frac{\Delta r_1}{\Delta r_2}$ (f) versus mould separation (h, mm)

Figure 5: $\frac{r_1}{r_2}$ (e) versus mould separation (h, mm)

$$\dot{\epsilon}_{yy} = \frac{eu}{(e+f)h} \quad (4)$$

$$\dot{\epsilon}_{zz} = -\frac{u}{h} \quad (5)$$

where u is the mould closing speed (squeezing rate) and h is the plate separation or the gap between the two mould plates.

Figure 6: Schematic of the specimen before and after squeezing.

MATHEMATICAL MODELLING

The constitutive equations are now modified to allow for three different viscosities in three directions. The shear influence is neglected as the squeeze flow process is fully lubricated:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{xx} \\ \sigma_{yy} \\ \sigma_{zz} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 2\eta_1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 2\eta_2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 2\eta_3 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \dot{\epsilon}_{xx} \\ \dot{\epsilon}_{yy} \\ \dot{\epsilon}_{zz} \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} P \\ P \\ P \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

Equation 6 has 4 unknown parameters η_1 , η_2 , η_3 and the pressure P . The stresses in the x and y directions are zero because of the free traction surface, but the stress in the z direction is equal to the applied stress:

$$\sigma_{zz} = -\sigma_{applied} \quad (7)$$

In this work the problem will be taken a step further and the material can be considered as an orthotropic non-Newtonian material with three different independent viscosities, governed by the shear power-law:

$$\eta_1 = m_1 (2D : D)^{\frac{n-1}{2}} \quad (8)$$

$$\eta_2 = m_2 (2D : D)^{\frac{n-1}{2}} \quad (9)$$

$$\eta_3 = m_3 (2D : D)^{\frac{n-1}{2}} \quad (10)$$

where D is the deformation tensor matrix and takes the form:

$$D = \begin{bmatrix} \dot{\epsilon}_{xx} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \dot{\epsilon}_{yy} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \dot{\epsilon}_{zz} \end{bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

and the double dot product is:

$$D:D = \sum D_{ij}D_{ji} = \dot{\epsilon}_{xx}^2 + \dot{\epsilon}_{yy}^2 + \dot{\epsilon}_{zz}^2 \quad (12)$$

The non-Newtonian (power-law) model in this form is governed by 5 unknowns m_1, m_2, m_3, n and the pressure P , in three equations with three unknown parameters in each equation. This makes the solution more difficult than previously, necessitating more experimental data or modelling steps. Equation 6 can be written as:

$$\sigma_{xx} = 2m_1(2(\dot{\epsilon}_{xx}^2 + \dot{\epsilon}_{yy}^2 + \dot{\epsilon}_{zz}^2))^{\frac{n-1}{2}} \dot{\epsilon}_{xx} - P \quad (13)$$

$$\sigma_{yy} = 2m_2(2(\dot{\epsilon}_{xx}^2 + \dot{\epsilon}_{yy}^2 + \dot{\epsilon}_{zz}^2))^{\frac{n-1}{2}} \dot{\epsilon}_{yy} - P \quad (14)$$

$$\sigma_{zz} = 2m_3(2(\dot{\epsilon}_{xx}^2 + \dot{\epsilon}_{yy}^2 + \dot{\epsilon}_{zz}^2))^{\frac{n-1}{2}} \dot{\epsilon}_{zz} - P \quad (15)$$

The three equations in this case can not be solved for the 5 unknowns by knowing only the stresses and strain rates, but the problem might be approached as follows:

As mentioned earlier, the stresses in the x and the y directions are zero and the stress in the z direction is equal to the applied stress. Equations 13 and 15 can be merged together eliminating the pressure:

$$\sigma_{zz} = 2m_3(2(\dot{\epsilon}_{xx}^2 + \dot{\epsilon}_{yy}^2 + \dot{\epsilon}_{zz}^2))^{\frac{n-1}{2}} \dot{\epsilon}_{zz} - 2m_1(2(\dot{\epsilon}_{xx}^2 + \dot{\epsilon}_{yy}^2 + \dot{\epsilon}_{zz}^2))^{\frac{n-1}{2}} \dot{\epsilon}_{xx} \quad (16)$$

and equation 16 can be written as:

$$\sigma_{zz} = (2m_3\dot{\epsilon}_{zz} - 2m_1\dot{\epsilon}_{xx})(2(\dot{\epsilon}_{xx}^2 + \dot{\epsilon}_{yy}^2 + \dot{\epsilon}_{zz}^2))^{\frac{n-1}{2}} \quad (17)$$

This equation can also be written as:

$$-\sigma_{applied} = \left(2m_3 \frac{-u}{h} - 2m_1 \frac{fu}{(e+f)h} \right) (2(\dot{\epsilon}_{xx}^2 + \dot{\epsilon}_{yy}^2 + \dot{\epsilon}_{zz}^2))^{\frac{n-1}{2}} \quad (18)$$

Linearising equation 17 by taking the logarithm of both sides gives:

$$\log\left(\frac{\sigma_{applied}h}{u}\right) = \log\left(2m_3 + 2m_1 \frac{f}{e+f}\right) + \frac{n-1}{2} \log\left(2(\dot{\epsilon}_{xx}^2 + \dot{\epsilon}_{yy}^2 + \dot{\epsilon}_{zz}^2)\right) \quad (19)$$

Plotting $\log\left(\frac{\sigma_{\text{applied}} h}{u}\right)$ versus $\log\left(2(\dot{\epsilon}_{xx}^2 + \dot{\epsilon}_{yy}^2 + \dot{\epsilon}_{zz}^2)\right)$ gives a linear curve where the slope is $\frac{n-1}{2}$, Figure 7, and n can be determined from the slope as 0.5576.

At this stage, after characterising n , equations 13-15 are left with 4 unknowns, two of them are in each equation and the pressure P is one of the two unknowns in each equation. The hydrostatic pressure generated by the lubricated squeezing flow was previously confirmed by Davis et al [6] to be constant and was given by the equation:

$$\frac{\partial P}{\partial r} = \frac{\partial P}{\partial \theta} = \frac{\partial P}{\partial z} = 0 \quad (20)$$

The hydrostatic pressure is a function of the strain rate as shown by equations 13 and 14, but this does not contradict equation 20. The pressure is still constant within the squeezed material at constant mould separation and constant strain rate (closing speed).

The three extensional viscosities of the material can be calculated from the three shear viscosities at any closing speed, as follows:

$$\lambda_1 = 2\eta_1 + \frac{2\eta_2}{1 + \frac{\eta_2}{\eta_3}} = a_1(2D:D)^{\frac{n-1}{2}} \quad (21)$$

$$\lambda_2 = 2\eta_2 + \frac{2\eta_1}{1 + \frac{\eta_1}{\eta_3}} = a_2(2D:D)^{\frac{n-1}{2}} \quad (22)$$

$$\lambda_3 = 2\eta_3 + \frac{2\eta_1}{1 + \frac{\eta_1}{\eta_2}} = a_3(2D:D)^{\frac{n-1}{2}} \quad (23)$$

Substituting the shear expressions from equations 8, 9 and 10, the constants a_1 , a_2 and a_3 take the following values:

$$a_1 = 2m_1 + \frac{2m_3m_2}{m_3 + m_2}, \quad a_2 = 2m_2 + \frac{2m_3m_1}{m_3 + m_1} \quad \text{and} \quad a_3 = 2m_3 + \frac{2m_2m_1}{m_2 + m_1} \quad (24)$$

Numerical values for the three shear parameters m_1 , m_2 and m_3 can be calculated for any mould separation by knowing the pressure. Then the three extensional parameters a_1 , a_2 and a_3 can also be calculated as shown in equation 24 above. Equations 8-10 can be used to calculate the three shear viscosities and equations 21-23 can be used to calculate three extensional viscosities. To conclude, the hydrostatic pressure is needed to be experimentally measured in order to characterise GMT material as an orthotropic material.

Figure 7: Logarithmic plot of equation 18 where n is determined from the slope and the interception is a combination of m_1 and m_3 .

CONCLUSIONS

GMT material behaved anisotropically under compression moulding as the circular specimens deformed into elliptical specimens. This research study focused on modelling the squeezing flow process with three different viscosities in three different directions. The elliptical deformation indicated a relationship between the two in-plane extensional viscosities but further investigations of the fibre orientation and structure [4, 7] suggested that the third direction (through thickness) should also be treated independently with a third viscosity.

The models and the work procedure presented in this paper can be repeated for different mould separations and the three extensional viscosities can be calculated and presented as a function of the closing speed (squeezing rate) and/or the mould separation (h).

Experimentally measuring the hydrostatic pressure as a function of strain rate is needed for this model to be successfully applied. Further work will be focused on modifying the experimental set up to allow for pressure transducers.

Nomenclature

a_1, a_2 and a_3 : Extensional viscosity power-law constants (Pa.s)

e : Ratio between the long and the short radius of the elliptical specimen.

f : Ratio between the increase in the long radius and the increase in the short radius.

h = The material thickness at any stage (m)

m_1 = Power law constant (Pa.s)

m_2 = Power law constant (Pa.s)

m_3 = Power law constant (Pa.s)

n = Power law index

P = hydrostatic pressure (Pa)

P_a = Atmospheric pressure (Pa)
 r_o = Initial specimen radius (m)
 r_1 = The long radius of the elliptic specimen, the major axis (m)
 r_2 = The short radius of the elliptic specimen, the minor axis (m)
 Δr_1 = The extension in the radius on the major axis (m)
 Δr_2 = The extension in the radius on the minor axis (m)
 u = The mould closing speed or squeezing rate (m/s)

Greek Letters:

$\dot{\epsilon}_{xx}, \dot{\epsilon}_{yy}$ and $\dot{\epsilon}_{zz}$ = Strain rates in x, y and z (1/s)
 λ_1 = In-plane viscosity in the major axis direction, x (Pa.s)
 λ_2 = In-plane viscosity in the minor axis direction, y (Pa.s)
 λ_3 = Extensional viscosity through thickness, z (Pa.s)
 η_1, η_2, η_3 = Fluid shear viscosities
 $\sigma_{applied}$ = Applied stress (N/m²)
 σ_{xx}, σ_{yy} and σ_{zz} = x, y and z components of the stress tensor (N/m²)

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